

Original Research

APPLICATION OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY IN PUBLIC HEALTHCARE SERVICE DELIVERY IN AKWA IBOM STATE.

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***Related declarations are provided in the final section of this article.*

Abstract

This study examined and evaluated the application of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in public healthcare service delivery within selected hospitals under the Akwa Ibom State Hospitals Management Board. The research was motivated by the increasing importance of digital technologies in improving efficiency, accuracy, and quality of healthcare services, particularly in developing health systems such as Nigeria's public healthcare sector. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. Both primary and secondary sources of data were utilized to ensure comprehensive coverage of the research objectives. Primary data were collected through the administration of semi-structured questionnaires to 260 respondents drawn from selected public healthcare facilities. A stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure proportional representation of different professional categories within the healthcare system, including doctors, nurses, pharmacists, laboratory scientists, and medical records personnel. Secondary data were obtained from relevant textbooks, journals, policy documents, and institutional reports. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistical tools, including percentages, while inferential analysis was conducted using the Chi-square (X^2) statistical method to test the stated hypotheses. The findings revealed that a majority of respondents strongly supported the use of ICT in healthcare delivery, acknowledging its positive impact on service efficiency, reduction in waiting time, improved referral systems, enhanced accuracy in diagnosis, and reduction in medical errors. The study further found that ICT tools such as computerized medical software, electronic medical records, and diagnostic technologies were present and actively utilized in the selected healthcare facilities. However, despite these advancements, the study identified gaps in infrastructure availability, staff capacity, and system optimization. The findings established a significant relationship between ICT adoption and improved healthcare service delivery in hospitals managed by the Akwa Ibom State Hospitals Management Board. The study concludes that ICT plays a vital

Article History

Received: 10 Apr 2026

Accepted: 07 May 2026

Published: 11 May 2026

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How to Cite

role in strengthening healthcare systems and improving service outcomes. It therefore recommends that government should provide adequate ICT infrastructure across all secondary healthcare facilities, including those in underserved and rural areas, while also ensuring continuous training and capacity development of healthcare personnel to enhance effective utilization of digital health technologies.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology (ICT); Healthcare Service Delivery; Public Health Sector; Electronic Medical Records; E-Health; Telemedicine; Hospital Management Board; Healthcare Efficiency.

Introduction

The role of the public service in Nigeria's development has long attracted reforms aimed at improving its efficiency and effectiveness. Over the years, successive governments have introduced various reform initiatives such as the Adebo Commission (1971), the Udoji Public Service Review Commission (1974), the Dotun Philips Civil Service Reform (1988), and the Allison Ayida Committee on Civil Service (1995). More recent efforts include the 1999 reforms under President Olusegun Obasanjo, which led to the establishment of the Bureau for Public Service Reform (BPSR), as well as later public sector reform initiatives under President Goodluck Jonathan, including the Vision 20:2020 development agenda (Ake, 2015; Ukwandu & Ijere, 2020). The central aim of these reforms has consistently been to improve the quality of public service delivery and strengthen the capacity of government institutions to perform core administrative functions that support sustainable national development (ECA, 2010). However, despite these repeated reform efforts, the Nigerian public service continues to struggle with inefficiency, weak institutional capacity, and poor service delivery. In practical terms, this has resulted in delayed, inadequate, and sometimes ineffective delivery of public goods and services to citizens (Dharma & Ali, 2014).

Against this backdrop, there is a growing need to improve service delivery systems in critical sectors such as healthcare through the integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). Globally, ICT has transformed healthcare systems by improving diagnosis, treatment, prevention, record management, and overall patient care. According to Burney et al. (2010), advances in ICT have significantly improved the quality and efficiency of medical services in recent years. Healthcare refers broadly to the diagnosis, treatment, and prevention of disease, illness, injury, and other physical or mental conditions. It is delivered through various professionals such as doctors, nurses, pharmacists, dentists, optometrists, and other allied health workers across primary, secondary, and tertiary levels of care. The effectiveness of healthcare delivery depends largely on the strength of the health system, which includes trained personnel, infrastructure, financing, and reliable health information systems. The World Health Organization (WHO) emphasizes that a well-functioning health system requires a skilled workforce, proper funding, reliable data systems, and efficient logistics for delivering quality care and medical technologies.

ICT plays a critical role in strengthening these health systems by improving access to information, reducing communication gaps, and supporting decision-making. It helps bridge the divide between healthcare providers and patients, as well as between health researchers and practitioners. ICT also enhances efficiency and reduces medical errors through electronic health

records, digital databases, and other health applications. As noted by Anyakoha (1991), ICT involves the use of electronic tools for collecting, processing, storing, and disseminating information, while Hawkrige (1983) describes it as a transformative force that has reshaped social and economic systems globally. In healthcare delivery, ICT enables innovations such as e-health and telemedicine, which improve access to medical services, particularly in underserved and rural areas. It also contributes to cost reduction, improved patient monitoring, and better health outcomes (Khan et al., 2012). For example, ICT tools allow patients to better understand their health conditions through visual and digital representations, improving communication between healthcare providers and patients (Rodrigues, 2014). Furthermore, studies have shown that ICT adoption enhances patient safety, reduces administrative costs, and improves overall service quality (Burney et al., 2010). Despite these benefits, many healthcare systems in developing countries, including Nigeria, have not fully integrated ICT into their operations. In Akwa Ibom State, for instance, many government hospitals still rely heavily on paper-based systems, with limited or no access to functional ICT infrastructure. This lack of digital integration continues to hinder efficient healthcare delivery. In addition, healthcare professionals often operate in resource-constrained environments, face limited access to professional development opportunities, and work without adequate support systems or digital resources. Although Nigeria has adopted a national ICT policy recognizing ICT as a catalyst for development, the implementation within the health sector remains weak. As a result, the potential benefits of ICT in improving healthcare delivery are yet to be fully realized in many public hospitals.

Statement of the Problem

The global rise of the digital revolution, driven by Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), has significantly transformed how societies communicate, work, govern, and deliver services. It has introduced new ways of creating and sharing knowledge, improved governance systems, and enhanced service delivery in sectors such as education, business, and healthcare (World Summit on the Information Society). In the healthcare sector, ICT has been widely recognized as a tool capable of improving efficiency, reducing costs, and enhancing patient outcomes. However, while developed countries have largely integrated ICT into their healthcare systems, many developing countries, including Nigeria, are still at the early stages of adoption (Castells, 2000). This has created a widening digital divide in healthcare delivery systems.

In Akwa Ibom State, government hospitals are yet to fully benefit from the advantages of ICT. Many facilities still operate without adequate digital infrastructure, and in some cases, without basic computer systems. Records are largely managed manually, which increases the risk of errors, delays in service delivery, and inefficiencies in patient management. Although ICT has the potential to improve access to healthcare services, support telemedicine, and enhance medical record management, its adoption in many public health institutions in the state remains very low. This situation is further worsened by limited technical skills among healthcare workers, inadequate funding, poor infrastructure, and lack of institutional support for ICT integration. There are also broader debates in the literature regarding the effectiveness of ICT in developing countries. While some scholars argue that ICT can bridge healthcare gaps and improve service delivery, others caution that unequal access, poor adaptation to local contexts, and infrastructural limitations may reduce its impact (Melkote & Steeves, 2001; Hanson & Narula, 1990). Given these challenges, this study seeks to examine the extent to which ICT has been adopted and utilized in healthcare service

delivery in selected public hospitals in Akwa Ibom State. It specifically aims to assess how ICT affects efficiency, quality of care, and overall service delivery within these healthcare institutions.

Aims of the study

The main objective of the Study is to examine and assess the application of information communication and technology in public healthcare service delivery in selected facilities under the Hospitals Management Board, Akwa Ibom State.

The specific objectives of the Study are:

- i. To identify the specific areas that special computer medical softwares are applied in the administration of public healthcare service delivery in selected healthcare facilities under the Hospitals Management Board, Akwa Ibom State
- ii. To examine the extent of the application of telemedicine technology in public healthcare service delivery in selected healthcare facilities under the Hospitals Management Board, Akwa Ibom State.
- iii. To assess the extent of application of healthcare technology in medical diagnostics in the selected healthcare facilities under the Hospitals Management Board, Akwa Ibom State.
- iv. To examine the extent of the application of electronic medical records in public healthcare service delivery in the selected healthcare facilities under the Hospitals Management Board, Akwa Ibom State.

Research Questions

- i. What specific areas are special computer medical software applied in the administration of public healthcare service delivery in selected healthcare facilities under the Hospitals Management Board, Akwa Ibom State?
- ii. How is telemedicine technology applied in public healthcare service delivery in selected healthcare facilities under the Hospitals Management Board, Akwa Ibom State?
- iii. How is healthcare technology applied in medical diagnostics in selected healthcare facilities under the Hospitals Management Board, Akwa Ibom State?
- iv. How are electronic medical records applied in public healthcare service delivery in selected healthcare facilities under the Hospitals Management Board, Akwa Ibom State?

Hypotheses

- Ho1 Ho There is no significant relationship between the application of special computer medical software's and the administration of public healthcare service delivery in facilities under Hospitals Management Board.
- Ho2 There is no significant relationship between the application of Telemedicine technology and public healthcare service delivery in facilities under Hospitals Management Board.
- Ho3 There is no significant relationship between the application of healthcare technology in medical diagnostics and public healthcare service delivery in facilities under Hospitals Management Board.
- Ho4 There is no relationship between the application of electronic medical records and public healthcare service delivery in facilities under Hospitals Management Board.

Review of Conceptual Framework

Concept of ICT in health sector

ICT in the prosperity region can be used alternately with the term e-prosperity or prosperity information development which contains telemedicine and Clinical informatics. Changing from a paper based for record keeping and reference purposes in our prosperity region to a PC based approach will be a remarkable idea since it will go far in getting patient information and keeping it safer in case of fire or any emergency Burger et al (2017). In cutting edge countries, everyday lifestyle is by and by ICT-driven and in the accompanying two or three years, it appears regular presence and experiences will be furthermore portrayed and refined by the gig of ICTs in the overall population. With e-prosperity procedure, clinical benefits suppliers can without a doubt got to clinical records and cures speedily without going through lots of reports put on racks. With the usage of ICT in prosperity region, various issues, for instance, the time spent by the patients keeping it together for their turn, missing cards and records of patients, nonappearance of information, and so on will be settled and there will be better help for the patient. The chance of perseverance will similarly be high and adequate thought will be given to people since there is more information about them that will rush the expert's work to satisfy the patients ('Bahlol, et al. 1997)

As of late, ICT is a device of articulation for medical care laborers like clinical specialists, medical attendants, clinical research facility researchers and radiologists in current medical care. ICT has become very much acclimatized into medical services conveyance framework particularly in created nations that couple of specialists can envision a day without involving PCs or organization with the end goal of counteraction of sickness and injury, advancement and upkeep of wellbeing, help of torment and enduring, care and fix of those with disease, evasion of sudden passing, and quest for a tranquil demise (Olorode & Oladunni, 2017).

Through the web, it is feasible to set up offices for concentrated patient checking administration which can empower specialists to watch their patients at a remote website, screen their important bodily functions progressively as well as offer guidance for medicines. ICTs can likewise be utilized for trade of data between various wellbeing experts. Medical procedure can be made simpler and more successful by empowering specialists to envision the region of the body that will be the subject of the activity by utilizing endoscope, filtered pictures of growths or other mechanical gadgets to help careful mediations with negligible difficulties. Nonetheless, it is essential to bring up that deficiency of ICT in wellbeing frameworks won't just hamper a singular's social and financial turn of events, yet additionally they might cause hindering impacts on public monetary possibilities particularly in emerging nations like Nigeria. The new Coronavirus episode on the planet has caused monetary slump and nearly brought to end financial exercises around the world (Ndukwe, 2004)

The Nigerian government has proposed a nonexclusive and binding together Wellbeing ICT system that can be utilized to create interest for an increment to work on the nature of wellbeing administrations and execution of suitable IT arrangements in wellbeing.(Gambo and Soriyan, 2017). Part of the ways of accomplishing this design is the foundation of the Public Wellbeing Advancement Strategy in 2016, which made an ICT division to help the wellbeing area electronically through digitizing and computerizing the different medical care processes. The Approach additionally gives strong foundation and specialized help for arrangements with the assistance of the Government Service of Correspondence, Administrative Service of Science and

Innovation, Office of the Head of Administration of the League and Public Data Innovation Advancement Organization.(Nwankwo, 2017).

The Use of ICT in Health Sector

The integration of computers into hospital practice has transformed healthcare delivery and can be broadly categorized into four main areas: clinical applications, administration, research, and community healthcare services. Each of these areas demonstrates how ICT enhances efficiency, accuracy, and overall quality of care.

i. Clinical Applications

In clinical practice, ICT is widely applied in patient assessment, monitoring, documentation, telemedicine, and electronic medical records (EMR). These systems improve the systematic collection, storage, and retrieval of patient information, leading to more accurate diagnosis and better-informed clinical decisions. In critical care units such as emergency departments, ICU, CCU, and NICU, ICT enables continuous real-time monitoring of patients' vital signs. It also enhances nursing documentation through standardized templates, improves accuracy in record-keeping, and ensures proper discharge summaries. Telemedicine further extends healthcare access by enabling remote consultations and diagnostic services, thereby improving specialist availability and reducing geographical barriers (Gambo & Soriyan, 2017). EMR systems significantly enhance healthcare delivery by providing instant access to comprehensive patient records, including medical history, treatments, allergies, and diagnostic reports (Shriniwas, 2004). They improve workflow efficiency, support clinical decisions, and facilitate functions such as billing, quality assurance, and health reporting. Compared to paper-based systems, EMRs reduce storage requirements, minimize duplication, improve data accuracy, and ensure continuity of care (Boccanelli & Dormond, 2006; Fitzpa, 2009).

Furthermore, Clinical Decision Support (CDS) systems enhance clinical practice by providing real-time alerts, reminders, and evidence-based guidelines that support accurate decision-making and reduce medical errors (Klein, 2006). Computerised Physician Order Entry (CPOE) systems improve efficiency and safety by allowing electronic ordering of medications, tests, and referrals, thereby eliminating errors associated with handwritten prescriptions. Similarly, electronic prescribing (e-prescribing) improves medication safety through automated checks for drug interactions, allergies, and dosage accuracy. Health Information Exchange (HIE) systems further strengthen healthcare delivery by enabling secure sharing of patient data across facilities using standardized and interoperable digital frameworks, while maintaining data privacy and security.

ii. Administration

In healthcare administration, ICT systems are used for financial management, budgeting, and cost analysis. Software applications such as Microsoft Excel and QuickBooks assist administrators in tracking operational costs, analyzing income and expenditure, and ensuring financial accountability. These systems also support payroll processing, tax deductions, and expenditure monitoring, thereby improving transparency and efficiency in hospital operations. ICT tools also enhance billing systems by ensuring accurate documentation and tracking of financial transactions. Furthermore, quality assurance systems rely on ICT to

monitor compliance with healthcare standards and improve service delivery. Human resource management is also improved through digital systems that integrate administrative and clinical roles, leading to more efficient hospital operations.

iii. Research

In medical research, computers play a vital role in data collection, analysis, simulation, documentation, and education. Electronic databases provide researchers with quick access to large volumes of medical literature, improving the efficiency and scope of research activities. Advanced search tools allow targeted retrieval of information based on authors, topics, or keywords, thereby enhancing precision and relevance. Computers also support the formatting, editing, and dissemination of research findings, reducing the time required for academic writing and publication. The widespread availability of online journals has further strengthened ICT's role in research communication. Additionally, e-learning platforms, online lectures, video tutorials, and simulation tools have transformed medical education by enabling flexible and interactive learning experiences.

iv. Community Healthcare Settings

In community healthcare delivery, ICT is used for health data collection, appointment scheduling, home care management, and remote patient monitoring. Hospital databases store information on disease trends, patient demographics, and geographic distribution, which supports data-driven decision-making and public health planning. Appointment scheduling systems improve efficiency by reducing waiting times, balancing patient flow, and prioritizing cases based on urgency (Idowu et al., 2013). Home care systems allow individualized care plans to be stored and updated electronically, helping patients manage medications and daily health activities more effectively. Remote patient monitoring systems provide continuous observation of patients with chronic conditions, such as cardiovascular diseases. Devices like electrocardiograms (ECG) transmit real-time data to healthcare providers, enabling early detection of abnormalities and timely intervention (Adebayo & Ofoegbu, 2014; Idowu et al., 2021).

Benefits of Application of ICT in Health Sector

Nigeria, with a rapidly growing population of over 190 million people and heavy reliance on government-owned hospitals, requires a more efficient and responsive healthcare delivery system to meet citizens' needs (Ndukwe, 2004). In this context, Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is essential for improving healthcare services, supporting planning, and enhancing overall system performance. One key advantage of ICT in the Nigerian health sector is improved communication between patients and healthcare providers. Through telehealth and e-health platforms, patients can access medical information online without physically visiting hospitals, helping to reduce overcrowding and long waiting times while allowing healthcare professionals to focus on critical cases (Gambo & Soriyan, 2017). ICT also enhances collaboration among medical professionals globally, improving knowledge sharing, research, and patient outcomes. ICT is also valuable for monitoring patient health. It enables the collection and analysis of large volumes of medical data, including patient history and clinical records, which supports accurate diagnosis and treatment (Boccanelli & Dormond, 2006). Health professionals can track disease outbreaks, share treatment guidelines, and monitor patient progress more effectively. In addition, ICT tools allow for

better sharing of scientific data among healthcare workers, improving overall service delivery (Aworinde, 2019).

Another important benefit is the efficient storage and retrieval of patient records. ICT systems allow medical records to be stored digitally, making it easy to access patient history, previous diagnoses, and prescribed treatments. Modern medical equipment such as body scanners, ECG machines, and pulse oximeters are ICT-enabled and help improve diagnosis and treatment accuracy (Mimbi & Bankole, 2015). In more advanced systems, electronic prescriptions are stored digitally and accessed securely by pharmacists, reducing errors and improving safety (Fitzpa, 2009). ICT also improves efficiency in healthcare delivery by saving time, reducing resource waste, and strengthening referral systems. It enables telemedicine, allowing doctors to consult or even perform procedures remotely. ICT-connected hospitals can quickly transfer patient records and test results to specialists, ensuring faster and more accurate treatment decisions, especially in emergencies (Idowu et al., 2013; Adebayo & Ofoegbu, 2014). Finally, ICT contributes to patient safety by reducing medical errors. Digital health platforms and intelligent systems support accurate diagnosis and treatment by providing access to large databases of medical knowledge. In some cases, robotic-assisted surgery guided by remote specialists can be used for life-saving operations, further reducing risks and improving outcomes (Idowu et al., 2021)

Concept of Public service delivery

Olowu (2002) describes service delivery as the fundamental purpose of the public service, arguing that government exists primarily to provide services that the private sector may not supply or that citizens may not be able to afford. In this sense, public administration is expected to meet social needs in a way that ensures accessibility and fairness. Similarly, Ahmed (2005) explains service delivery as a long-standing concept that reflects an organisation's responsibility to provide services to clients in the most efficient and satisfactory manner. In the public sector context, this relationship places citizens as the "clients" and government agencies as service providers, where performance is judged based on factors such as quality, timeliness, cost, communication, and accessibility.

Ahmed (2011) further outlines the expectations of Nigerians from the public service, which include professionalism, courtesy, responsiveness, transparency, accountability, efficiency, punctuality, and fairness. It also includes proactive communication, prompt handling of complaints, and a strong commitment to reducing corruption, waste, and inefficiency. Citizens also expect affordable services, well-maintained infrastructure, and continuous improvement based on public feedback. However, Ahmed (2005) notes that at the beginning of Nigeria's democratic transition in 1999, the public service was widely viewed in negative terms. It was commonly described as slow, inefficient, corrupt, unresponsive, poorly disciplined, and resistant to change, with low regard for time management and public accountability.

Empirical studies

Gupta and Jana (2003), in their study titled *ICT in Public Administration and Service Delivery*, examined why ICT adoption is essential for improving government operations and public service delivery. The study adopted a conceptual and analytical methodology based on a review of existing literature, with no specific population, sample size, or sampling technique as it was theoretical in nature. Data were drawn from secondary sources such as journals, policy papers, and institutional reports and analyzed through content and thematic analysis. The study found that ICT is not

optional but a necessity for efficient governance and improved service delivery. It recommended full integration of ICT into public administration systems to enhance efficiency and responsiveness. The study is relevant to the present work as it establishes ICT as a core requirement for effective public service delivery in civil service systems, including Nigeria.

The European Commission (2003), in its study titled *The Role of ICT in Enhancing Good Governance in Public Sector Administration*, examined how ICT improves governance, transparency, and efficiency in public institutions across EU member states. The study used a descriptive policy analysis approach without a defined population, sample size, or sampling technique. Data were obtained from secondary sources such as government reports and ICT implementation frameworks and analyzed through qualitative policy evaluation. The findings revealed that ICT enhances transparency, accountability, efficiency, citizen participation, and reduces delays and errors in service delivery. The study recommended the adoption of ICT systems to strengthen governance and citizen engagement. It is relevant to this study as it provides a theoretical foundation for understanding ICT's role in promoting transparency and accountability in public service delivery.

Ndou (2004), in the study *E-Government for Developing Countries: Opportunities and Challenges*, explored the impact of e-government systems on public administration efficiency in developing countries. The study adopted a qualitative review and comparative analytical approach using secondary data from global ICT and governance reports. No specific population, sample size, or sampling technique was applied. The findings showed that e-government reduces administrative bottlenecks, improves information sharing, eliminates manual errors, and enhances the speed and accuracy of service delivery. The study recommended investment in ICT infrastructure and capacity building for effective e-government implementation. This study is highly relevant as it supports the argument that ICT improves efficiency in public service delivery in developing countries like Nigeria.

Nweke (2007a; 2007b), in the study *ICT Application and Public Service Reform in Nigeria*, investigated the role of ICT in improving public service delivery, efficiency, and governance reform in Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive research design supported by policy analysis, with no specified population, sample size, or sampling technique. Secondary data were collected from government publications and policy documents and analyzed using qualitative content analysis. The findings revealed that ICT enhances administrative efficiency, reduces service delays, improves transparency, and strengthens accountability in the public sector. The study recommended intensified ICT integration across all government ministries and agencies. It is highly relevant to this work as it focuses directly on ICT implementation within the Nigerian civil service.

Muchie (2011), in the study *ICT, Governance and Citizen Participation in Developing Countries*, examined the role of ICT in enhancing governance transparency and citizen participation. The study adopted a qualitative analytical design using secondary data sources such as policy documents and academic literature. There was no defined population, sample size, or sampling technique. Data were analyzed thematically. The study found that ICT improves transparency, accountability, responsiveness, and promotes citizen engagement in governance processes. It recommended the adoption of e-governance systems to strengthen democratic participation. The study is relevant to the present research as it highlights ICT's role in improving citizen participation in public service delivery systems.

Theoretical framework

The theoretical foundation of this study is anchored on the Modernization Theory of Development, which provides a useful lens for understanding how Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) influence public service delivery. The theory explains development as a progressive transformation from traditional, low-income, and less structured societies to modern, technologically advanced, and highly efficient systems (Melkote & Steeves, 2001). In this context, ICT is viewed as a key driver of modernization, capable of transforming governance structures, improving institutional efficiency, and enhancing service delivery outcomes in developing countries such as Nigeria. Modernization theory, which emerged in the 1940s and 1950s, is one of the earliest and most influential perspectives in development studies (Servaes, 1999). It assumes that underdeveloped societies can achieve development by adopting the values, technologies, and institutional structures of developed Western nations. Early scholars such as Lerner (1958) argued that exposure to Western media and communication systems would help traditional societies overcome “backwardness” and adopt modern ways of thinking and organizing social life. In this regard, mass communication and technology were seen as powerful tools for stimulating economic growth, political participation, and social transformation (Thussu, 2000).

From this perspective, ICT is considered a vital instrument for accelerating development by facilitating the transfer of modern knowledge, skills, and administrative systems from advanced to developing societies. Modernization theorists argue that ICT promotes economic efficiency, improves governance, and enhances public service delivery by replacing outdated manual systems with automated and digital processes. This belief has influenced global development policies, where ICT is often promoted as a solution to administrative inefficiency, poor service delivery, and weak institutional capacity in developing countries (Melkote & Steeves, 2001). Furthermore, the theory emphasizes centralized planning and the role of government and international institutions in driving development. Organizations such as the United Nations, World Bank, and International Monetary Fund often support ICT-based reforms in developing countries based on the assumption that such technologies will improve governance and economic performance (Nulens & Van Audenhove, 1999). In Nigeria, this has been reflected in the adoption of e-government initiatives aimed at improving efficiency, transparency, and accessibility in public service delivery.

However, modernization theory has been widely criticized for its overemphasis on external technological transfer and its assumption that development is a linear process of copying Western models. Critics argue that technology is not culturally neutral and cannot simply be transferred without considering local social, economic, and institutional contexts (Kranzberg in Castells, 2000). Dependency theorists further contend that such technological adoption can increase reliance on developed countries rather than promote true self-sustained development (Servaes, 1999). They argue that ICT adoption in developing countries may reflect a form of Westernization rather than genuine modernization, as it often imports not only technology but also foreign administrative values and systems. Despite these criticisms, modernization theory remains relevant to this study because it provides a foundational explanation of how ICT is expected to improve public service delivery in the Nigerian Civil Service. It supports the view that the adoption of modern ICT systems can enhance administrative efficiency, reduce bureaucratic delays, improve transparency, and strengthen overall governance performance

Methodology

The study adopted a survey research design because it focuses on the use of questionnaires to capture respondents' perceptions of existing conditions. The design is appropriate for describing and interpreting prevailing problems, practices, and relationships, as well as for eliciting opinions, beliefs, attitudes, and emerging trends. In addition, the study incorporated both quantitative and qualitative approaches, with the questionnaire survey complementing the broader research strategy. The population of the study comprised staff of the Hospitals Management Board (HMB), Akwa Ibom State, based on the second-quarter nominal roll. The HMB has a total staff strength of 2,155 personnel distributed across 43 secondary healthcare facilities. However, five hospitals were purposively selected for the study based on high patient attendance and the level of government subvention received for their operations. From these selected facilities, a total population of 745 staff was obtained for the study.

The study population consisted of health professionals in the selected public hospitals in Akwa Ibom State. These included doctors, nurses, medical laboratory scientists, pharmacists, medical records officers, and other allied health workers. Stratified random sampling was employed to ensure adequate representation of the different professional categories within the healthcare system. This approach enhances representativeness and allows for statistical generalisation of findings with an acceptable margin of error. The study focused on key departments and units within the selected hospitals, including medical records, accident and emergency, outpatient and inpatient services, medical laboratory services, and pharmacy units. These departments were selected because they represent critical points of patient care and service delivery within the healthcare system. To determine the sample size, the Yaro Yamane formula was applied, assuming a confidence level of 95%. This method was used to ensure an appropriate and statistically valid sample size from the study population.

$$n = N / (1 + N(e)^2)$$

Where n = Sample size

N = Population = 745

e = Standard error or allowable error = 0.05

$$n = 745 / (1 + 745(0.05)^2)$$

$$n = 745 / (1 + 1.8625)$$

$$n = 745 / 2.8625$$

$$n = 260 \text{ respondents}$$

Therefore, based on the above calculation, the sample size population of the study is 260 respondents.

Table 1: Determination of sample size of the study

Institution	Population	Sample size
Methodist General Hospital, Ituk Mbang	137	47
General Hospital, Ikot Ekpene	207	73
General Hospital, Iquita, Oron	149	52
Immanuel General Hospital, Eket	149	52
General Hospital, Etinan	103	36
Total	745	260

Source: Field survey, 2023.

The sample size population for the study as could be seen from the table is 260. It is from this sample survey that the results of the study will be generalised, therefore, much has been done so that the sample will reflect its nature as accurately as possible.

Results

A total of two hundred and sixty (260) questionnaire forms were administered to respondents, and all were duly retrieved, representing a 100% response rate. Therefore, the sample size for the study consisted of 260 respondents. The responses obtained from the questionnaire were comprehensive and provided relevant information for the study analysis.

Hypothesis One

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the application of specialised computer medical software and the administration of public healthcare delivery.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the application of specialised computer medical software and the administration of public healthcare delivery.

To test the hypothesis, data generated from respondents on the use of computer medical software in improving healthcare delivery were analysed. The Chi-square (X^2) statistical technique was employed to determine the level of association between the variables under study.

$$= \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Where \sum = Summation

O = Observed Frequency

E = Expected Frequency

X^2 = Chi Square

Table 2: Testing of Hypothesis One : There is no significant relationship between the application of special computer medical softwares and the administration of public healthcare service delivery in facilities under Hospitals Management Board.

Response Category	O	E	O - E	(O - E) ²	$\frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$	Degree of freedom	Significance level	Critical value	Calculated value
Strongly Agreed	135	52	83	6,889	132	4	0.05	9.488	236
Agreed	82	52	30	900	17				
Undecided	3	52	-49	2,401	46				
Disagreed	26	52	-26	676	13				
Strongly Disagreed	14	52	-38	1,444	28				
Total	260	260			236				

Source: Field survey, 2023

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

$$= 236$$

The calculated Chi-square (X^2) value was 236.

To determine the decision rule, a significance level of 0.05 was adopted, and the degree of freedom (df) was computed as $n - 1$, where n represents the number of response categories. Thus, $df = 5 - 1 = 4$. The corresponding critical value from the Chi-square table at 0.05 significance level and 4 degrees of freedom is 9.488.

Decision Rule: Since the calculated value of 236 is greater than the critical value of 9.488, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion: There is a significant relationship between the application of specialised computer medical software and the administration of public healthcare delivery.

Hypothesis Two

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the application of telemedicine technology and the administration of public healthcare delivery.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the application of telemedicine technology and the administration of public healthcare delivery.

To test this hypothesis, data relating to the use of telemedicine in enhancing healthcare delivery in the selected healthcare facilities were analyzed using the Chi-square (X^2) statistical method to determine the level of relationship between the variables.

Using Chi-square (X^2)

$$= \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Where \sum = Summation

O = Observed Frequency

E = Expected frequency

And the expected frequency in a one-way table = Sample size/ number of categories.

Using 0.05 level of significance

Degree of Freedom = n - 1, where n is the number of categories.

Table 3: Testing of Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between the application of Telemedicine technology and public healthcare service delivery in facilities under Hospitals Management Board.

Response Category	O	E	O - E	(O - E) ²	$\frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$	Degree of freedom	Significance level	Critical value	Calculated value
Strongly Agreed	115	52	63	3,969	76.3269	4	0.05	9.488	205
Agreed	100	52	48	2,304	44.3077				
Undecided	3	52	-49	2,401	46.173				
Disagreed	26	52	-26	676	13				
Strongly Disagreed	16	52	-36	1,296	24.923				
Total	260	260			204.731				

Source: Field survey, 2023

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

$$= 205$$

The calculated Chi-square (X²) value is 205.

To determine the decision rule, a significance level of 0.05 was adopted, and the degree of freedom (df) was computed as n - 1, where n = 5. Therefore, df = 5 - 1 = 4. The corresponding critical value from the Chi-square distribution table at 0.05 level of significance and 4 degrees of freedom is 9.488.

Decision: Since the calculated value of 205 is greater than the critical value of 9.488, the null hypothesis is rejected while the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This implies that there is a significant relationship between the application of telemedicine technology and the administration of public healthcare delivery.

Hypothesis Three

H₀: There is no significant relationship between the application of healthcare technology in medical diagnostics and the administration of public healthcare delivery.

H₁: There is a significant relationship between the application of healthcare technology in medical diagnostics and the administration of public healthcare delivery.

To test this hypothesis, data obtained from Frequency Table 4.20 on the use of healthcare technology in medical diagnostics and its effect on healthcare delivery in the selected healthcare facilities were utilized. The Chi-square (X^2) statistical method was employed to determine the relationship between the variables under study.

$$= \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Where \sum = Summation

O = Observed Frequency

E = Expected frequency

X^2 = Chi Square

Table 4: Testing of Hypothesis Three :

Response Category	O	E	O - E	(O - E) ²	$\frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$	Degree of freedom	Significance level	Critical value	Calculated value
Strongly Agreed	115	52	63	3,969	76.3269	4	0.05	9.49	201
Agreed	95	52	43	1,849	35.5577				
Undecided	3	52	-49	2,401	46.173				
Disagreed	20	52	-32	1,024	19.6923				
Strongly Disagreed	17	52	-35	1,225	23.5577				
Total	260	260			201.308				

Source: Field survey, 2023

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

$$= 201.3$$

Therefore, calculated value = 201.3

To know whether to accept or reject the null hypothesis, we take the significant level as 0.05 and the degree of freedom (DF), n - 1, which is 5 - 1 = 4

Critical value = 9.488

Decision:

Since the calculated value of 201.3 is greater than the critical value of 9.488, we reject null hypothesis which says there is no significant relationship between the application of healthcare technology in medical diagnostics and the administration of public healthcare delivery.

Testing of Hypothesis four

Ho There is no relationship between the application of electronic medical records keeping and the administration of public healthcare delivery.

Hi There is a relationship between the application of electronic medical records keeping and the administration of public healthcare delivery.

Data recorded in Table 4.24 Use of Electronic Medical Records Keeping Enhances Healthcare Delivery in the Selected Healthcare Facilities are implored in the testing of this Hypothesis using Chi-square.

Using Chi-square (X^2)

$$= \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Where \sum = Summation

O = Observed Frequency

E = Expected frequency

X^2 = Chi Square

Response Category	O	E	O - E	(O - E) ²	$\frac{(O - E)^2}{E}$	Degree of freedom	Significance level	Critical value	Calculated value
Strongly Agreed	99	52	47	2,209	42.4807	4	0.05	9.49	114.1
Agreed	80	52	28	784	15.0769				
Undecided	1	52	-51	2,601	50.0192				
Disagreed	35	52	-17	289	5.5577				
Strongly Disagreed	45	52	-7	49	0.9423				
Total	260	260			114.077				

Source: Field survey, 2023

$$X^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

$$= 114.1$$

Therefore, calculated value = 114.1

To know whether to accept or reject the null hypothesis, we take the significant level as 0.05 and the degree of freedom (DF), n - 1, which is 5 - 1 = 4

Critical value = 9.488

Decision:

Since the calculated value of 114.1 is greater than the critical value of 9.488, we reject the null hypothesis which says there is no relationship between the application of electronic medical records keeping and the administration of public healthcare delivery.

Discussion of findings

The aim of this study was to examine the use of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in the delivery of public healthcare services in selected facilities under the Akwa Ibom State Hospitals Management Board. The findings indicate that ICT has the capacity to significantly transform healthcare delivery by improving efficiency, accuracy, and effectiveness within the health system, thereby enhancing patient safety and service quality. However, the successful implementation of ICT requires specialized skills, meaning healthcare professionals must adapt their clinical workflows and invest time in acquiring ICT competencies. As noted by Kahan (2000), ICT in healthcare provides critical linkages, supports clinical decision-making at the point of care, and enables continuous quality monitoring, making it one of the fastest-growing sectors in health service delivery. The study further revealed that ICT applications improve the speed of medical diagnostics and enhance access to health information. This is reflected in improved clinical decision support systems and better collaboration among healthcare professionals, which ultimately strengthen workflow integration and patient care outcomes. These findings align with Adeleke et al. (2015), who observed that ICT adoption improves coordination among healthcare workers and enhances patient satisfaction.

Results also showed a generally positive level of ICT utilization in the selected healthcare facilities. A majority of respondents indicated that ICT tools such as electronic medical records, telemedicine systems, computer-based diagnostic tools, and specialized medical software are actively used to improve healthcare delivery. This demonstrates that ICT infrastructure is not only available but also being applied in service delivery processes within the studied facilities. Despite these benefits, the study identified several challenges affecting effective ICT implementation. A key limitation is inadequate training and retraining of healthcare personnel, which hinders effective utilization of ICT systems. Respondents also highlighted poor maintenance of ICT infrastructure as a constraint to efficient service delivery. These findings are consistent with Zerriffi (2011), who noted that insufficient technical skills among healthcare workers contributes significantly to resistance and inefficiency in ICT adoption in healthcare systems.

Another major challenge identified is the issue of unstable electricity supply. Respondents noted that inconsistent power supply from the national grid limits the continuous use of ICT systems in healthcare facilities. Additionally, hardware and software failures were reported to disrupt system functionality, thereby affecting service delivery. These findings are supported by Adu (2013), who emphasized that unreliable power supply and system breakdowns pose serious threats to effective ICT utilization in healthcare. This study therefore contributes to knowledge by serving as a reference point for future research on ICT and healthcare service delivery in developing countries. It establishes that modernization theory, information society theory, and diffusion of innovation theory are interconnected in explaining how ICT influences healthcare systems, particularly in addressing social and institutional challenges. Collectively, these theories provide a strong conceptual foundation for understanding ICT-driven healthcare transformation and stakeholder expectations within the system. Furthermore, the study highlights the need for developing countries to adopt an appropriate mix of technologies in healthcare delivery. This

includes combining modern ICT systems with locally available or indigenous technologies to ensure broader accessibility and relevance. Such an approach enhances inclusiveness and ensures that digital healthcare solutions reach both urban and rural populations effectively. Additionally, forming strategic partnerships with key stakeholders and developed countries can help reduce costs, improve capacity building, and facilitate access to advanced ICT infrastructure, thereby strengthening healthcare delivery systems in resource-constrained environments

Conclusion

This study examined the role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in public healthcare service delivery within selected facilities under the Akwa Ibom State Hospitals Management Board. Findings indicate that ICT is rapidly reshaping healthcare systems and has become a critical component in the delivery of modern medical services. Its application enhances efficiency, accuracy, and effectiveness in healthcare operations while significantly improving patient safety and service quality. The study further established that ICT facilitates improved access to healthcare services, particularly for underserved and rural populations. However, the realization of its full potential depends on the availability of adequate infrastructure, skilled personnel, and sustained institutional support. Bridging the digital divide between urban and rural healthcare facilities remains essential, especially through the expansion of broadband connectivity and modern ICT infrastructure. Overall, ICT presents a viable pathway for strengthening healthcare delivery, although its effectiveness is constrained by infrastructural and capacity-related challenges.

Recommendations /Policy Actions

i. Strengthening ICT Infrastructure and Capacity Building

Government should ensure the provision of robust ICT infrastructure across all healthcare facilities, including underserved areas, while also investing in continuous training and retraining of healthcare personnel to improve competence in the use of medical software and digital health technologies.

ii. Improvement of Connectivity and Power Supply Systems

There is a need to expand reliable broadband internet access across both rural and urban healthcare facilities, possibly through fiber-optic networks and regulatory policies requiring telecom providers to support health institutions. In addition, alternative energy sources such as solar or wind power should be adopted to ensure uninterrupted ICT operations in healthcare facilities.

iii. Policy Development, Regulation, and Technology Integration

The government should develop and enforce comprehensive policies guiding ICT implementation in healthcare, including regular updates. Emerging technologies should be integrated into healthcare delivery systems, software applications should be made more user-friendly with automated features, and legal frameworks should be strengthened to ensure data privacy and effective ICT governance in the health sector.

Article Publication Details

This article is published in the **OpenMind Journal of Multidisciplinary Innovation & Development**, ISSN 3108-2920 (Online). In Volume 2 (2026), Issue 3 (May - Jun) - 2026

The journal is published and managed by **OMR PUBLICATION** .

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Acknowledgements

We sincerely thank the editors and the reviewers for their valuable suggestions on this paper.

Authors' contributions

All author(s) read and approved the final manuscript.

Funding

The author(s) declare that no funding was received for this work.

Data availability

No datasets were generated or analyzed during the current study.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

The author(s) declare that not applicable.

Consent for publication

The author(s) declare that not applicable.

Competing interests

The author(s) declare no competing interests.

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